

USING PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS

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Abstract. This paper explores the benefits of using interactive pedagogical technologies in educating foreign languages. It includes the short list of methods and technologies which can be useful in developing language skills of the english language learners.

Keywords: communicative, method, project – based learning, English, approach

INTRODUCTION

The background to this paper is one where the author carried out research of numerous secondary science textbooks, curriculum documents and made use of transcripts of video recordings of English-medium and mother-tongue Science lessons. There is analysed practical and effective technologies such as project – base learning, team spirit.

MAIN PART

The main objective of foreign language teaching is the formation and development of the communicative culture of pupils, learning practical mastery of a foreign language. The task of the teacher is to create the conditions of practical language learning for each student to choose such training methods that would allow each student to show their activity, their creativity. Modern teaching techniques such as cooperative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources help to realize the learner centered approach to learning, providing personalization and differentiation of learning abilities of children, taking into account their level of training. The communicative approach is a strategy that simulates the communication, aimed at creating a psychological and linguistic readiness to communicate, on a conscious understanding of the material and methods of action with him. For the user, the implementation of the communicative approach in the Internet is

not particularly difficult. Communicative job must offer students a problem or question for discussion, and students do not just share information, but also evaluate it. But the main criterion to distinguish this approach from other types of learning activities is that students choose their own linguistic units to process their thoughts. Using the Internet in the communicative approach could not be better motivated: its aim is to interest students in learning a foreign language through the accumulation and expansion of their knowledge. One of the basic requirements for teaching foreign languages using the Internet resources, is to create interaction in the classroom, what is called in interactive methods. Teaching genuine language, the Internet helps in shaping the conversation, as well as in teaching vocabulary and grammar, providing a genuine interest and, hence, efficiency.

Project method is one of the most pressing contemporary technologies in teaching foreign languages. It combines the elements of problem-based learning and collaborative learning that allows achieving the highest level of mastery of any subject, and foreign language in particular. Project method forms students' communication skills, culture, communication, the ability concisely and audibly formulates thoughts, be tolerant to the opinion of partners in communication and develops the ability to extract information from a variety of sources, to process it with the help of modern technologies.

References:

1. Innovative technologies of teaching foreign languages // Молодой ученый. — 2018. — №5. — С. 182-184. — URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/191/48195/> (дата обращения: 14.02.2020).
2. Akzhan M. Abdyhalykova* Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Vol 9(22), DOI: 10.17485/ijst/2016/v9i22/95561, June 2016
3. Akimov, V.B. (2010). Orhanizatsiia informatsionno-tekhnicheskoho prostranstva uchebnoho zavedeniia. Media-biblioteka, interaktivnye doski [Organization of information and technical space of the educational institution. Media

library, interactive whiteboards]. Volgograd: Uchitel [in Russian].

4. Ayatov, R., & Sherov, D. (2020). Improving the Conversational Process in Foreign Language Teaching. *International Engineering Journal for Research and Development*, 5(1),32-37.

5. Babadjanova, N. (2020). Effective Classroom Management Techniques for Curriculum of 21st Century. *Science and Education*, 1(7).